

Compare the Effectiveness of Deflazacort and Prednisolone in Idiopathic Nephrotic Syndrome in Children

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Abstract:

Background: Nephrotic syndrome is a manifestation of glomerular disease characterized by severe proteinuria, hypoalbuminemia and hyperlipidemia. It affects numerous children globally with idiopathic syndrome being the most common form in pediatric population. The therapeutic effectiveness and safety profiles of prednisolone and deflazacort in treating this condition necessitate further examination.

Methodology: 100 patients were enrolled in this study between 1 to 10 years old who were diagnosed with idiopathic nephrotic syndrome. This study was conducted at BRD Medical College, Gorakhpur, for six months. Patients were randomly registered to receive either deflazacort or prednisolone.

Results: Both treatments were effective in inducing remission with deflazacort, showing a slightly higher remission rate but no significant differences were found in growth parameters between the groups. Although, deflazacort was associated with some complications and adverse effects as compared to prednisolone. Both drugs significantly improved laboratory values such as ESR and protein/creatinine ratio with notable reductions in plasma urea and creatinine.

Conclusion: Deflazacort may be considered as more favorable with efficacy and safety in the treatment of pediatric idiopathic nephrotic syndrome as compared to prednisolone.

Keywords: Nephrotic syndrome, Deflazacort, Prednisolone.

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Introduction

A frequent glomerular condition in children, idiopathic nephrotic syndrome (INS) is defined by oedema, severe proteinuria, hypoalbuminemia, and hyperlipidaemia. Between the ages of two and six, the majority of instances occur [1]. The first line of treatment for INS is corticosteroids (CS). The prognostic value of this disease is best predicted by the patient's response to CS therapy. Relapses, however, are a common feature of the clinical course of NS; 70–80% of children with INS who are initially diagnosed will have at least one relapse following the cessation of CS.

Nevertheless, the majority of individuals with steroid-sensitive INS experience a long-term, treatment-free remission as they mature, making the long-term prognosis favourable. But the literature doesn't specify the precise age at which there is no longer a considerable risk of relapses. While NS seems to resolve in many cases during

puberty, other patients continue to relapse far into adulthood. According to early research on the natural course of childhood INS, only 5% of kids will experience relapses that are severe enough to last throughout adulthood [2]. But there are notable differences in the rates of persistent illness between the trials [3-7].

Some of these studies found that the number of relapses in childhood and adolescence and the need for second-line therapy were risk factors for relapses in adulthood. It is still unknown why some patients with NS continue to relapse into adulthood and whether the length of the disease or puberty and sex hormone effects the resolution of NS. The majority of these studies focused largely on individuals who kept relapsing and were single-centered. Seventy-six percent of idiopathic NS cases are in subjects with minimal change disease (MCD) [8,9]. Although 95% of these patients

respond well to steroids, 75% relapse, and 50% of them (those who relapse frequently or who are steroid-dependent) need larger, longer-acting doses of steroids, which raises the possibility of adverse effects (4). In steroid-resistant individuals, prednisolone (PDN) is substituted with different CS (deflazacort, methylprednisolone), in combination with immunosuppressive medications. Relapses generally decrease in frequency as children get older [10,8].

Deflazacort is one of the other corticosteroids that have been synthesized more recently with the primary goal of creating novel medicines that are more tolerable in every age range. As a heterocyclic corticosteroid and an oxazoline derivative of prednisolone, deflazacort has been shown in multiple clinical studies to have high efficacy and good tolerability in conditions where corticosteroid treatment is indicated. These studies have also assessed the drug's safety.

Deflazacort's structural features, in particular, can account for some of its unique pharmacological effects, such as its significant lack of sodium-retaining activity, potent anti-inflammatory/immunosuppressive activity, and reduced interference with phosphocalcium and carbohydrate metabolism (and, consequently, on growth and bone turnover) when compared to earlier corticosteroids [11].

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at the B.R.D Medical College, Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, in the Department of Pharmacology and IPD (in -Patients

Department), Department of Pediatrics. The patients were enrolled in the study who were diagnosed cases of nephrotic syndrome of 1 to 10 years old with written informed consent. The institutional ethical committee gave its approval before the study could be carried out. Subsequent tests were performed to confirm the diagnosis, including a 24-hour urine total protein test, serum albumin, serum cholesterol, and urine for R-M/E.

Intervention

The study conducted in two groups group I and Group II, each group has 50 patients. Group I received deflazacort orally for 6 weeks as 2.4mg/kg/day in three divided doses per day to treat initial incident of idiopathic syndrome. 1.8 mg/kg/day doses were administered as a single morning dosage on alternate days. Group II received prednisolone orally for six weeks with 2 mg/kg/day in three divided doses to treat initial attack after that next 6 weeks patients were recommended for 1.5 mg/kg/day for alternate days in the morning time.

Results

In the present study the 1 to 2 years age group showing the maximum patients with 47 patients and minimum patients were in 6 to 9 years age group with 6 patients. The number of male patients were higher than female patients with 57 and 43 respectively. According to nephrotic syndrome condition the 100% patients were of facial edema but the number of microscopic haematuria were 57% and gross haematuria with lowest number with 8% only.

Table 1: Showing the distribution as per age, gender and nephrotic syndrome associated conditions

Age wise distribution		
Age Groups	No. of Patients (n = 100)	Percentage
1 – 2 years	47	47.0%
3 – 5 years	32	32.0%
6 – 9 years	6	6.0%
10	15	15.0%
Gender wise distribution		
Male	57	57%
Female	43	43%
Distribution according to nephrotic syndrome associated conditions		
Facial Edema	100	100%
Microscopic Haematuria	57	57%
Gross Haematuria	8	8%

Table 2: Distribution of study participants according to various parameters

S No.	Parameter	Group A (Deflazacort)	Group B (Prednisolone)	P Value
1.	Weight (kg)	14.21 ± 3.28	17.94 ± 10.03	0.232
2.	Height (cm)	93.87 ± 8.79	102.80 ± 23.66	0.231
3.	Weight and Height ratio	0.15 ± 0.02	0.16 ± 0.05	0.437

Table 3: Distribution of study participants according to outcome parameter

Outcome Parameter	Group A (Deflazacort) (Sample size: 50)	Group B (Prednisolone) (Sample size: 50)	P Value
Remission rate	50 (100%)	42 (84.6%)	0.480
Time to induce remission, days	10.25 ± 2.4	12.55 ± 1.44	0.012
No. of relapses on follow up	5 (10%)	14 (28%)	0.586
Change in weight (kg)	1.36 ± 0.96	1.38 ± 0.56	0.958
Change in height (cm)	2.13 ± 0.50	1.44 ± 0.45	0.003
Change in weight height ratio	0.01 ± 0.010	0.01 ± 0.006	0.931

Above table is showing participant distribution on the basis of outcome characteristics reveals notable distinctions between group A and group B, especially with the duration required to produce remission and the alteration in height. With 50 participants, Group A had a 100% remission rate, while Group B was showing 84.6% (P=0.480). With a P value of 0.012, Group A induction period for remission was substantially shorter (10.25 ± 2.4

days) than Group B (12.55 ± 1.44 days). Group A saw fewer relapses (10%) during follow-up than Group B (28%); nevertheless, this difference was not statistically significant (P=0.586). The weight/height ratio (P=0.931) and weight change (1.36 ± 0.96 kg for Group A and 1.38 ± 0.56 kg for Group B, P=0.958) were similar for both groups. The change in height showed significant difference in group A in contrast to group B (P=0.003).

Table 4: Distribution of study participants according to change in urine protein and urine creatinine ratio

Treatment	Baseline Mean	Baseline Standard Error	End point Mean	Endpoint Standard Error	P-Value
Prednisolone	97.5	5.8	71.2	3.1	<0.0001
Deflazacort	132.2	15.9	81.7	6.6	<0.00053

Distribution of participants according to the change in urine protein and urine creatinine ratio. Participants treated with prednisolone showed a decrease in the mean ratio from baseline value with a standard error of 5.8, to 71.2 (Endpoint) with a standard error of 3.1, resulting in a significant P-

value of <0.0001. Meanwhile, those treated with deflazacort experienced a reduction in the mean ratio from baseline value with a standard error of 15.9, to 81.7 (Endpoint) with a standard error of 6.6 which showed a significant P-value of <0.00053.

Table 5: distribution of study participants according to change in plasma urea

Condition	Time Point	Mean	P Value
Prednisolone	Baseline	50.46	<0.0001
	Endpoint	40.61	<0.001
Deflazacort	Baseline	60.66	0.017
	Endpoint	43.95	<0.05

Participants undergoing treatment with prednisolone and deflazacort. In the prednisolone group, initial mean plasma urea levels of 50.46 mg/dl with significant decrease to 40.61 mg/dl (p-values <0.0001 initially and <0.001 at endpoint). Similarly, for participants treated with deflazacort, baseline

plasma urea levels of 60.66 mg/dl significant decreased to 43.95 mg/dl, (p-values of 0.017 initially and <0.05 at the endpoint).

This data illustrates the effectiveness of both treatments in reducing plasma urea levels, with statistical significance.

Table 6: Distribution of study participants according to change in plasma creatinine

Values	Prednisolone Baseline	Prednisolone Endpoint	Deflazacort Baseline	Deflazacort Endpoint
Mean	1.28	1.04	1.55	1.13
SEM	0.09	0.07	0.15	0.10
SD	0.89	0.63	0.76	0.53
P Value	<0.0001		0.03	

Present study showed plasma creatinine levels decreased significantly from baseline to endpoint in participants treated with prednisolone (from 1.28 to 1.04 mg/dL, P < 0.0001) and deflazacort (from 1.55 to 1.13 mg/dL, P = 0.03) indicating effective renal function improvement with both treatments.

Table 7: Distribution of study participants according to change in plasma total protein.

Condition	Time point	Mean	P Value
Prednisolone	Baseline	4.7	<0.0001
	Endpoint	5.26	
Deflazacort	Baseline	4.89	0.0088
	Endpoint	5.34	

The change in plasma total protein levels, differentiated by treatment condition and time point. In the prednisolone group, the mean plasma total protein level increased from 4.7 at baseline to 5.26 at the endpoint with a statistically significant change indicated by a p-value of <0.0001. Similarly, in the deflazacort group, the mean level increased from 4.89 at baseline to 5.34 at the end point with this change, data also showed statistically significant as denoted by a p-value of 0.0088.

Discussion

In children with idiopathic nephrotic syndrome, this study sought to examine the safety and effectiveness of deflazacort with prednisolone. Results suggest that deflazacort may have some clinical benefits over prednisolone, especially in terms of growth impact and remission induction time.

Compared to prednisolone, deflazacort showed a quicker time to remission (10.25 ± 2.4 days) (12.55 ± 1.44 days, $P = 0.012$). This discrepancy might point to a benefit of utilising deflazacort for quicker illness control, which is especially advantageous for kids to reduce long-term steroid exposure. Despite the high remission rates in both groups, Group A (deflazacort) had a 100% remission rate, while Group B (prednisolone) had an 84.6% remission rate; however, this difference was not statistically significant ($P = 0.480$). Furthermore, although the deflazacort group saw decreased relapse rates (10% vs. 28%), the difference was not statistically significant ($P = 0.586$). This pattern is consistent with other studies that found deflazacort to be effective in lowering the incidence of relapses in steroid-dependent nephrotic syndrome (Broyer et al., 1997) [12].

Significant height differences were found by anthropometric measurements, with Group A exhibiting a larger height increase (2.13 ± 0.50 cm) than Group B (1.44 ± 0.45 cm, $P = 0.003$). The effect of deflazacort on height indicates that it may have a less suppressive effect on growth than prednisolone, even though both groups showed similar weight changes and weight-to-height ratios. This is consistent with research by Broyer et al. (1997), which found that children treated with deflazacort showed improved growth patterns. Renal indicators showed significant improvements. Both groups experienced a significant decrease in the urine protein-creatinine ratio ($P < 0.0001$ for prednisolone; $P < 0.00053$ for deflazacort), with

deflazacort demonstrating a larger drop from baseline in instances of higher beginning proteinuria. Both groups' plasma urea and creatinine levels decreased statistically significantly, suggesting that both therapies were successful in promoting renal recovery. Nonetheless, the deflazacort group showed larger relative decreases, indicating that it might be beneficial for individuals with more severe renal impairment, even if they began with higher baseline levels (Hahn D., et al., 2024) [13].

Both groups showed a considerable improvement in plasma protein levels, which was indicative of better hypoalbuminemia and less protein loss. The mean plasma total protein in patients treated with deflazacort increased significantly from 4.89 to 5.34 g/dL ($P = 0.0088$), whereas in the prednisolone group, it grew from 4.7 to 5.26 g/dL ($P < 0.0001$). This implies that both therapies are successful in controlling hypoalbuminemia, which is a crucial aspect of treating nephrotic syndrome (Claudio P. et al., 2023) [14].

Conclusion

The study involved 100 children with the age group 1–2 years having the highest representation at 47%. Males constituted 57% of the participants, indicating a slightly higher male involvement in the study. All participants experienced Facial Edema, highlighting it as a common condition among those with Nephrotic Syndrome. Significant variations were observed in the age characteristics and responses to treatments between two groups, one treated with Deflazacort and the other with Prednisolone.

No statistically significant differences were found in weight, height, and weight/height ratio between the two treatment groups. Group A (Deflazacort) had a higher remission rate and a faster time to induce remission compared to Group B (Prednisolone). Significant reductions in Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR) and Urine Protein/Creatinine Ratio were noted post-treatment, suggesting effectiveness in reducing inflammation and improving kidney function. Plasma urea, creatinine, and total protein levels significantly improved post-treatment in both treatment groups. The study also documented various complications associated with the treatments, with gastritis being the most prevalent.

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